

The Name of Thai Muslim Students: The Reflection of Value and Identity of Thai Muslim

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Abstract—To study the meaning of Muslim name in order to analyze the underlining value and identity from first year to fourth year Muslim students at Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai Campus. The questionnaires are employed as a main analytical tool to acquire the names from 80 Muslim students in four study years. The meanings of obtained names are subsequently analyzed and summarized base upon related documents to uncover the beneath value. The study reveals that name of male is derived from the name of prophet; Nabi Muhammad, merit, dignity, origins, leadership and the faith in Islam. For female, on the other hand, their names are related to virtue and beauty, cleanliness and peace, hope and flowers which comply with their characteristics. One of the reasons contribute to the principle of naming is the regulation of Ministry of Culture which states that the name should represent one's nature and characters. The given name reflects value and identity of Muslim which can be classified into three categories including 1) Value related to belief in Islam 2) value related to relationship among families and relatives 3) value about relationship with nature and environment. All the above mentioned reflect Muslim value and identity vividly. The name of Muslim students allows the researcher to perceive the perspective, belief and value in giving the name of Thai Muslim. Besides, it reveals social condition and their culture. It can also be the fundamental of studying the meaning of name in other races.

Keywords—The naming, Thai Muslim.

I. INTRODUCTION

NAME is a crucial part of life representing its owner. It is a short word compromising parents' supervision to their newborn. Giving the name is considered as one of the most important matter of life [1]. Parents, therefore, choose the fortunate name to their children with the belief that when people call that name, the virtue will be accumulated [2]. The language used to name the person can be studied not only in terms of the language characters but also the relationship between the language itself and society, the language and culture [3], [4]. However, it is obvious that religion plays one of the most important roles on differentiating the language in giving name. Furthermore, it indicates belief, value and different culture of each race. The researcher are, consequently, interested in studying the contributing factors, which includes belief and value, to name giving of Thai Muslim students who are studying in 2013 from first year to fourth year at Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai Campus where a number of Muslim students from many provinces are gathered on the basis of ethnic Semantics.

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A. Aim

To conceal the meaning, value and Identity reflected from the name of Muslim students.

B. Terms and Definition

- 1) The meaning of name means the meaning according to word form except the name of Thai Muslim that is derived from the name of the Muhammad or related people. Nonetheless, if the word is developed from Arabian or Melayu, the original meaning can be maintained.
- 2) Value means the idea and behaviors that are accepted and practiced by people in society from time to time.
- 3) Uniqueness means individual identity that indicates characteristic of Thai Muslim.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Respondents

80 Muslim students from first year to fourth year of Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai campus in 2013 with the equal percentage of both genders.

B. Instrument

Quantitative Research is applied as an instrumental method for further analysis where the closely-monitored questionnaires are distributed to respondents in order to acquire accurate and realistic information.

C. Data Analysis

Obtained data is critically analyzed with the application of percentage and frequency.

III. FINDINGS

A. The Meaning in Giving Name

According to the name of 80 Muslim students, it can be categorized according to the meaning as presented in the table.

TABLE I
THE FREQUENCY OF THE MEANING IN GIVING NAME

Meaning	Number of students	Percentage
Merit and virtue	14	17.5
Name of prophet or persons related to prophet	13	16.25
Dignity popularity and admiration	7	8.75
Light and Hope	7	8.75
Flower and plants	7	8.75
Cleanliness, peace and happiness	6	7.5
Knowledge and Ability	5	6.25
Origin and family	4	5
Honesty and Faith	3	3.75
Power and victory	3	3.75
Brave and endeavor	2	2.5
Woman	2	2.5
Place	2	2.5
Adornment and accessories	2	2.5
Animal	1	1.25
Number	1	1.25
Relationship	1	1.25
Total	80	100

TABLE II
THE FREQUENCY OF MEANING USED IN GIVING NAME BASE UPON GENDER

Meaning	Male		Female	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Merit and virtue	5	12.5	9	22.5
Name of prophet or persons related to prophet	12	30	1	2.5
Dignity popularity and admiration	5	12.5	2	5
Light and Hope	2	5	5	12.5
Flower and plants	3	7.5	2	5
Cleanliness, peace and happiness	-	-	6	15
Knowledge and Ability	2	5	5	12.5
Origin and family	4	10	-	-
Honesty and Faith	1	2.5	2	5
Power and victory	1	2.5	2	5
Brave and endeavor	2	5	-	-
Woman	-	-	2	5
Place	1	2.5	1	2.5
Adornment and accessories	1	2.5	1	2.5
Animal	-	-	1	2.5
Number	-	-	1	2.5
Relationship	1	2.5	-	-
Total	40	100	40	100

According to the table, the meaning used in giving name can be divided into 17 categories. The frequency are illustrated by percentage as following

1. Frequency between 8%-17%

The most popular meaning in name giving falls into merit and virtue which counts for 17.5%. The second popular is the name of prophet; Nabi Muhammad and his children or other people related with him at 16.25%, followed by the meaning regards dignity, popularity, admiration with the same frequency as the meaning related to light, hope and flower or plants at 8.75%

2. Frequency between 5%-7%

The highest percentage in this range falls into the meaning regarding cleanliness, peace and happiness which counts for 7.5%. The meaning about knowledge, ability and the meaning that represents origin and family gained 5% of popularity.

3. Frequency between 1%-3%

The meaning that has been used the most frequently is the meaning representing honesty, faith and maintenance, which counts the same percentage as the meaning about power and victory at 3.75%. The second largest in the range belongs to the meaning related to brave and endeavor as well woman and place at 2.5%. The meaning about animal, number and relation gain the least popularity at only 1.25%

The following table presents the frequent use of meaning in name giving categorized by gender

It can be concluded from the studied result that the meaning related the name of prophet; Nabi Muhammad and his children or other people related with him presents the largest percentage of all at 30% while the merit and virtue, dignity, popularity and admiration follow as the second largest at 12.5%. The next popularity belongs to the name with the meaning regards origin and family at 10%. The meaning about knowledge and ability gains 7.5%. The meaning regards hope, flower, plants, brave and endeavor has got 5% and The least frequent meaning belongs to those which are related to honesty, faith, power, victory, place, adornment and accessories and relationship at only 2.5%. However, the meaning about cleanliness, peace, happiness, woman, animal and number is not found.

In terms of female name, the meaning regarding merit and virtue is the most common with 22.5% of frequency. The second popular meaning is related to cleanliness, peace and happiness which count for 15%. Followed by the meaning about light and hope which acquire the same percentage as the meaning about flower and plant at 12.5%. The meaning of knowledge, ability, dignity, popularity, admiration, honesty, faith, power, victory and woman are at 5%. The least applicable meaning falls into the meaning of the name of prophet; Nabi Muhammed and his children or other people related with him, adornment and accessories, animal and number at only 2.5%. The there is no record about the name with the meaning of origin, family, brave, endeavor and relationship.

B. Value in Naming

Name represents value, social condition and unique or Muslim students which can be presented into 3 categories

- 1) Value about belief in Islam; Muslim students have a tight bond with Islam religion. For them, Islam is not just a religion, yet it is the whole life and soul. They regard it as a fundamental of living and well-being. These students, therefore, comply strictly to the Islamic principal which includes faith and morale as following
 - (1) The value reflecting faith; peace and fate such as Maisarah which means comfortableness and Zuhaira which means peaceful.
 - (2) Faith in prophets or people related with him; Such as Muhammad (Nabi's name) Abdulloh (son Allah)
 - (3) Knowledge and ability such as Afigoh (Wiseperson) Padeela (Excellent)
 - (4) Stability, honesty and faith such as Iman (faith person)
- 2) Value in terms of relative origins and family; Thai Muslim take this matter serious although it is slightly deteriorated these days. The names beginning with Je, Ni, Wan and Whan are derived from Melayu. It is an honorable name inheriting the state's governor in the past such as Nipadilah and Je Abdulloh.
- 3) Value represents relationship with nature and environment as following.
 - (1) Place such as TeraMiZi (the name of city) Zarohna(the name of village)
 - (2) Animal such as Sakulnee (bird)
 - (3) Plant such as Rossalan (Rice: the main food of Thais) Azaha (Rose: the symbol of love)
 - (4) Phenomenon such as Zamhiyah (the Sun) Dariyah (the light on the sky)The above value obviously reflects traditional lifestyles, cultures, identity and how university students live.

IV. DISCUSSION

It can be inferred that the value behind the name of Muslim students are not different from other race of Thais which include the value of relationship among family and relatives, origins, the value regards relationship between people and nature and environment, the value about morale. However, the value that best reflects Muslim's identity is the value about the belief in Islam.

Thai Muslim believes that Islam is their lives and the fundamental of living. Fellow who conform to the Muslim's principal will definitely become happy. The merit from behaving well will bring virtue to their family. The deep faith together with abiding love of Muslim is consequently presented in the name of their descendants. The value representing relationship of family and origins reflects the connection of family unit. It is the connection that beyond the rule of religion. The value about environment and nature reveals their perception about the importance of surrounding toward their lives [5], [6].

V. CONCLUSION

The study "The name of Muslim Thai students: The Reflection of value and uniqueness of Muslim Thai" is conducted on the purpose of studying the meaning, value and

identity reflected from Muslim students' name. The study results state as following

A. The Meaning Used in Naming

The study result states that all things fortunate are obtained to name the person, not only abstract idea but also concrete objects. The most common belongs to the meaning about merit and virtue, followed by the meaning of the prophet's name and the meaning about dignity, light, flowers or plants whereas the meaning regarding place, animal, number and relationship are deployed the least frequently. When considering from variable; gender, the principal of naming in female and male presents the significant difference as illustrated below

Male: the name of prophet; Nabi Muhammed> merit, beauty, dignity> origins or family

Female: merit, beauty > cleanliness, peace > light and flowers.

B. Value in Naming

The value that is reflected from the meaning of Muslim name can be categorized into four types; (1) The value about the belief in Islam (2) The value about morale (3) The value about family relationship and (4) The value about the relationship with nature and environment.

It is true to conclude that name is the vital factor that reflects the value, society and uniqueness of Thai Muslim.

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